

CRACK PROPAGATION/DEFLECTION IN THE INTERPHASE OF SiC/SiC CERAMICS MATRIX CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

SiC continuous fiber reinforced SiC ceramic matrix composites (CMC) are of great interest as a structural material for hot section gas turbine jet engine components because of their high strength, low thermal conductivity and relative low density when compared to Ni-base superalloys. Toughness of SiC/SiC CMCs in these applications is a key consideration, and the strength and bonding characteristics of the fiber coating or interphase have a significant influence on the overall CMC performance. For example, Rebillat et al. [1] demonstrated that changes in the interphase strength and the bonding characteristics between the fiber coating and the fiber can potentially double the overall tensile strength of a SiC/SiC CMC with a BN coated fiber. Overall, the interphase has many functions including promotion of crack deflection when matrix cracks intersect the fibers, load transfer between the fibers and matrix and protection of the fibers from environmental attack. Optimizing the interphase properties for these multiple functions necessitates a detailed understanding of the fracture process at the fiber/matrix interface.

Multiple models have been proposed to predict crack propagation versus deflection at the filament scale in CMCs. Based on the principles of fracture mechanics, He and Hutchinson [2] assuming an isotropic material defined the criterion for crack deflection at the fiber-matrix interface according to

$$\frac{G_d}{G_p} < \frac{\Gamma_i}{\Gamma_f} \quad [1]$$

where G_d and G_p are the energy release rates for deflection and propagation and Γ_f and Γ_i are the critical energy release rates or surface energies for

the fiber and for a deflecting crack at interface between two semi-infinite planes. Later Martinez and Gupta [3] included the effect of anisotropy and showed that the energy for a doubly deflected crack is higher than that for a singly deflected crack in certain cases. He et al. [4] later corrected their result for the doubly deflected crack and also considered the influence of residual stress. Tullock et al. [5] performed numerical calculations which showed similar results. Additionally, Ahn et al. [6] numerically considered the influence of crack extensions with the same criteria defined in Equation 1 and predicted that crack deflection requires more energy for finite crack extension and finite fiber volume fraction than previously shown in the limit of zero fiber volume fraction or infinitesimal crack extension as calculated analytically by He et al. [4]. However, none of these approaches account for the presence of an interphase region of finite thickness. Consideration of the interphase by Martin et al. [7], via fracture mechanics implemented in a finite element model predicted enhanced crack deflection in the presence of a interphase with low toughness at the fiber-interphase interface. Additionally, in the absence of an interphase, they predicted that crack deflection is enhanced if the toughness of the matrix is less than that of the fiber; previous studies neglected any toughness mismatch between the fiber and matrix. Effect of interphase modulus was confirmed by Parthasarathy et al. [8] using FEM, who also reported an additional effect from the thickness of the interphase layer.

Although these previous studies offer some insight into the fundamental damage process at the scale of the individual fibers, these models consider only one single dominant crack intersecting the fiber-matrix or matrix-interphase interface. In a

variety of materials, secondary debonding or cracking at the interphase or at interphase boundaries at some distance in front of the primary crack has been observed, which results in retarded or arrested growth of the primary crack [9-12]. In fact, such a crack deflection mechanism was postulated much earlier by Cook and Gordon [13]. Here interfacial debonding was predicted ahead of the crack tip as a result of the stress component parallel to the crack plane σ_{rr} if the interface is sufficiently weak. For an elliptical crack, σ_{rr} is maximal at a distance ahead of the crack tip on the order of the crack tip radius. Pagano and Brown [10] simulated cracking with and without the secondary cracking or interfacial debonding mechanism and predicted much higher energy release rates in the case of debonding of the interface ahead of the crack tip. Additionally Pompidou and Lamon [14], used the basis of the Cook and Gordon model [13] to estimate the propensity for the interface ahead of the crack tip to debond based on the elastic mismatch and relative strengths of the fiber and matrix. Even though these approaches considered secondary cracking in the interface, the finite interphase thickness was not considered. Additionally, the Cook and Gordon model [13], which was the basis of the model by Pompidou and Lamon [14], assumes an elliptical crack with finite radius. In reality, matrix cracks are not elliptical and can be quite sharp, resulting in a much different stress state ahead of the crack tip. Finally, depending on the strength of the interphase, bonding between the matrix and interphase or interphase and fiber, cracks perpendicular to the crack plane can initiate in the interphase further ahead of the crack tip than where σ_{rr} is maximum.

In this work, the extended finite element method, XFEM, [15-17], implemented in Abaqus, [18], is employed to study fiber/matrix crack deflection in SiC/SiC CMC with a BN coating over the fibers. Unlike the above treatises, the weak fiber coating is explicitly modeled as having a finite thickness. Material properties of a commercially produced SiC/SiC CMC (HiPerComp®) were taken as the basis for the simulations with different variations of strength for matrix, coating, and fiber. Simulations were performed in 2D using plain strain elements. Preliminary simulations were also performed with 3D continuum elements. Reduced integration was not employed in any of the simulations. The fracture

energy of the interface between the matrix/interphase and interphase/fiber was taken to be the same as the interphase (the weakest phase).

2 Simulation Strategy

In the simulations performed here, the fiber (SiC), matrix (SiC) and fiber coating (BN) were explicitly modeled with the strength of the matrix being less than that of the fiber as shown experimentally, [19]. Initial crack (or crack like defects in 3D simulations) was incorporated to study crack propagation characteristics as the cracks approach the fiber/matrix interface. Loading in all the simulations was strain-controlled with uniform displacements applied on the boundaries parallel to the initial crack. All the other boundaries were traction free.

Table 1. Properties of HiPerComp® SiC-SiC CMCs [19].

Matrix
Elastic properties E=360 GPa , $\nu=0.185$
Initiation stress $\sigma_i=0.8$ GPa (maximum principal)
Fracture energy 36 J/m ²
Tolerance 0.05; Damage stabilization 0.005
Coating (BN)
Elastic properties E=10 GPa , $\nu=0.05$
Initiation stress $\sigma_i=75$ MPa (maximum principal)
Fracture energy 5 J/m ²
Tolerance 0.05; Damage stabilization 0.01
Fiber
Elastic properties E=380 GPa , $\nu=0.185$
Initiation stress $\sigma_i=2.6$ GPa (maximum principal)
Fracture energy 50 J/m ²
Tolerance 0.05; Damage stabilization 0.005

Basic properties of the SiC/SiC CMCs were assumed to be those similar to that of the melt-infiltrated processed HiPerComp® material produced by GE Aviation [19]. The material properties employed in the simulations are summarized in Table 1. To evaluate the influence of damage initiation and propagation parameters on the behavior of the system a range of strengths were considered for the matrix and the fiber coatings. These values are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Variants of damage parameters

	σ_i	Fracture energy
Matrix	0.4 GPa	36 J/m ²
	0.8 GPa	
	1.2 GPa	
Coating	50 MPa	5 J/m ²
	75 MPa	10 J/m ²
	100 MPa	15 J/m ²
	150 MPa	
Fiber	2.6 GPa	50 J/m ²

Damage initiation is predicted base on a maximum principal stress initiation criterion. The numerical values of the initiation stresses for different materials used in simulations are given in Tables 1 and 2; these values are referred to as “strengths” of respective materials. Cohesive laws govern crack evolution, and fracture energy is the chosen parameters of cohesive laws employed. The numerical values of fracture energy for materials utilized in the simulations are given in Tables 1 and 2. Note that fracture energy here defines the evolution law that describes the rate at which cohesive stiffness is degraded once the initiation criterion is met. Thus, this model cannot be directly compared to the classical fracture mechanics where crack propagation is determined by energy release rate.

The modeling is quasi-static, which requires viscous regularization to overcome convergence difficulties in ABAQUS Standard (i.e, with implicit

integration). The material parameters for this stabilization are given in Table 1 (“damage stabilization”). In addition, a parameter “tolerance” is also employed. Specifically, if stress is within the tolerance from the crack initiation criterion, a crack will be initialized in an element, if the stress is above the tolerance limit, the time step will be decreased until the tolerance is met.

As can be seen in Table 1, there is a variety of mechanical parameters the system’s state depends upon, in addition to the geometric characteristics. The focus of this work was on the crack initiation and evolution parameters of the coating and the matrix. Fiber properties were not varied between any of the simulations. The thickness of the coating was taken to be 1 μm and did not change between simulations. The maximum principal stress criterion results in the crack initiating as close to the upper boundary of the coating layer as is possible (i.e., in the middle of the upper layer of elements in the coating layer). Thus, the simulations exhibit a slight mesh size dependence, which was observed to decrease as the element size was reduced.

The commercial FEA software package ABAQUS 6.12 was used for all of the simulations in this work. It is noted, however, that the implementation of XFEM in ABAQUS does not allow crack coalescence. This limitation did not allow simulation of the primary crack to join with the secondary cracks that initiated in the coatings. Instead, once the primary crack propagates to within an element or two of the secondary crack, either the primary crack continues to propagate in an unnatural manner (e.g. parallel to the coating), or arrays of additional cracks appear in the coatings that eventually propagate into the fiber. This behavior occurs because the elements between the tip of the main crack and the secondary crack become rigid, since no crack coalescence is numerically possible in the simulation. Because of this limitation of the XFEM implementation in ABAQUS, results of the simulations were only considered up to the point where the primary cracks grew to within 2 elements of the secondary crack.

3 Results/Discussion

For the applied loading and boundary conditions described above, the simulations in all cases

predicted secondary cracking at a finite distance ahead of the primary crack in the weak BN fiber coating. These secondary cracks that initiated in the BN fiber coating are then predicted to grow into the matrix as the primary matrix crack continues to propagate toward the interface between the matrix and fiber coating ahead of the secondary crack.

Typically, the following stages were observed in the 2D simulations with plane strain elements.

- 1) Growth of the primary crack
- 2) Secondary crack initiation in the coating ahead of the primary crack tip.
- 3) Crack propagation of the secondary crack growth in the coating until crack intersects with the matrix/fiber coating boundary. The primary crack continues to propagate but at a reduced rate.
- 4) The primary crack continues to propagate. The secondary crack does not transition into the matrix until the main grows to within a distance of the fiber coating on the order of the thickness the coating to about half of that width (1 μm).
- 5) At this point, the secondary crack starts to propagate into the matrix, with infinitesimal change in the applied displacement.

Some of the simulations proceed significantly further than the last stage described, however, as discussed previously the results are not physically meaningful when the main crack propagates to within a few elements of the secondary crack due to the limitations of this particular implementation of XFEM in ABAQUS that does not allow crack coalescence.

As far as the simulations were able to progress with the noted limitation of not being able to simulate crack coalescence, the simulations demonstrated that secondary cracking ahead of the primary crack tip in the fiber coating is an effective crack deflecting mechanism. The predicted response is not captured by the Hu-Hutchinson [2, 4] model and is oversimplified by the model of Cook and Gordon [13] or Pompidou and Lamon [14]. For example, Figure 1 shows that the fiber coating can initiate a secondary crack even when the approaching crack is at a distance much greater than the radius of the crack tip. This contradicts Cook and Gordon's result that the influence of the crack in the

matrix is limited to a process zone on the order of the crack tip radius [13]. Additionally, Figure 2 illustrates that the cracking mechanism in 3D arrays of multiple fibers distributed throughout a volume can be quite complex with multiple secondary cracks initiating ahead of the primary crack tip.

Figure 1. 2D XFEM simulation of SiC/SiC CMC showing crack approaching fiber matrix interface with secondary crack initiating finite distance from the crack tip in the BN fiber coating; (a) initiation of the crack; (b) growth of the secondary crack into the matrix deflecting the main crack from the fiber

Figure 2. 3D XFEM simulation of SiC/SiC CMC showing cracks initiating in the BN fiber coating when loaded in the transverse direction (i.e., normal to the fiber direction).

Matrix strength 1.2 GPa
 Coating strength 50 MPa
 Fracture energy (coating) 5 J/m²

(b)

Figure 3 . Displacement in the direction normal to crack for two different simulations

The distinctive *chevron* cracks observed in Figure 1 and Figure 3 resulted from the maximum principle stress crack initiation criterion employed in these simulations. Similar *en echelon* cracking has been observed experimentally [20-23]. In these instances, this cracking mechanism was observed to be localized within the fiber coatings and did not propagate into the matrix. In contrast, for the simulations performed here, the secondary crack propagated into the matrix when the applied strain exceeded a certain magnitude. We note that the simulated volumes were quite constrained and that the applied boundary conditions of these 2D plain strain simulations might not be representative of what actually occurs in 3D. It is also possible that the crack initiation and propagation criterion of max principle stress is not representative of the actual failure mode. Shear dominated failure modes could produce an alternate response. It is noted that the *en echelon* cracking observed experimentally was largely attributed to a Mode II type shear mechanism. Regardless, we consider the mechanisms observed here relative to the insight that can be gained from the relative properties for the applied boundary conditions and maximum principle stress failure criterion. Future work will consider a

Matrix strength 0.4 GPa
 Coating strength 75 MPa
 Fracture energy (coating) 10 J/m²

(a)

wider range of boundary conditions along with other crack initiation and propagation criteria.

To effectively compare the influence of the relative strengths of the matrix and fiber coating, a quantitative parameter was desired that would describe the relative effect of the different constituent strengths of the matrix and fiber coating that were considered. Although various energy approaches were considered, the primary measure of the influence of the relative constituent strengths of the matrix and fiber coating on secondary crack initiation and propagation was based on the length of the secondary matrix cracks measured perpendicular to the primary crack plane at the point in the simulation where the primary crack had propagated to within a few elements of the secondary crack.

Figure 4. The dependence of secondary crack length from the primary crack plane is given relative to the coating strength. The different matrix strengths are indicated in the legend.

The justification for use of this distance can be given with the following example. Compare the simulation in Figure 3(a) with a matrix strength of 0.4 GPa, coating strength of 7.5 MPa, and fracture energy (coating) of 10 J/m² to the simulation in Figure 3(b) with a matrix strength of 1.2 GPa, coating strength of 5 MPa, and fracture energy (coating) of 5 J/m². The overall strain in the simulation shown in Figure 3(a) is about 30 percent lower than in simulation given in Figure 3(b), but the secondary crack that initiated in the coating and that has grown into the matrix is significantly longer in Figure 3(a) than Figure 3(b). As a result, the combined crack that forms when the primary crack

coalesces with the secondary crack in Figure 3(a) is more likely to grow away from the fiber than in simulation Figure 3(b) because of the additional leverage provided by the longer crack branches. By this argument, the distance between the main crack plane and the crack tip of the secondary cracks is hypothesized to be an indicator that can be employed to quantify the differences between the simulations and how much deflection potential is provided by the formation and propagation of the secondary cracks.

By employing this criterion based on the length of the secondary crack, comparisons can be made as to the influence of the relative strengths of the matrix and fiber coating on the overall response. For example, as seen in Figure 4, for the simulations performed here, the difference in the matrix strength is more significant than the difference in the coating strength, although a closer look at the curves for matrix strengths of 0.8GPa and 1.2GPa suggests a slight increase with the increase in the coating strength.

Figure 5. The dependence of the distance between coating and the tip of the primary crack is given relative to the coating strength. The different matrix strengths are indicated in the legend.

An alternate method to analyze the simulations is to look at the applied strains or distances marking transitions between different regimes of deformation listed previously. For crack initiation, the distance from the primary crack plane is given in Figure 5 and applied strain is given in Figure 6 as a function of the various constituent properties.

The data in Figure 5 and Figure 6 is also grouped by the matrix strength. However, it can be observed similar to that in Figure 4 that the difference between matrix strengths 0.8 GPa and 1.2 GPa has less of an influence on the response than between the matrix strengths of 0.4 GPa and 0.8 GPa, respectively. It is pointed out in Figure 5 that for most of the simulations performed the secondary crack initiates in the coating at distances greater than the coating width (i.e., 1 μm). Another significant change in the deformation regime occurs at the point of “transition” where the secondary crack begins to propagate into the matrix. It is also significant that the tip of the primary crack in most of the simulations does continue to propagate closer to the secondary crack until the simulation becomes not physically meaningful or that the applied strain changes only infinitesimally; this suggests unstable crack growth. It is noted that the simulation is quasi-static and artificial viscous stabilization was employed in ABAQUS to promote convergence of the solution.

Figure 6. The dependence of applied strain at secondary crack initiation is given relative to the coating strength. The different matrix strengths are indicated in the legend.

The dependence of applied strain at which secondary crack moves into matrix (“transition” strain) is given relative to the coating strength in Figure 7. It can be observed that Figure 7 exhibits some correlation with Figure 4, which demonstrates the dependence of the increased length of the

secondary crack on the coating strength. Longer secondary cracks correspond to a lower “transition” strain or strain at the point the secondary crack begins to propagate into the matrix. Thus, the “transition” strain can be used for quantification in the same manner as the length of the secondary cracks relative to the plane of the primary crack.

4. Conclusions

A numerical study of the classical problem of crack propagation/deflection at an interface of dissimilar materials presented in this paper is observed to be quite complex. For the strengths of matrix fiber and coating chosen, the failure is always ahead of the crack tip and in the coating.

Numerical simulations with the FEM can produce results that are more representative of reality than analytical models, but the results can be difficult to interpret. Therefore, understanding the results is not straightforward, and requires parametric studies and quantification metrics that are not always obvious.

Figure 7. The dependence of applied strain at which secondary crack moves into matrix (“transition” strain) is given relative to the coating strength. The different matrix strengths are indicated in the legend.

The XFEM implementation in ABAQUS has been proven quite useful in the presented analysis, but it has its limitations. This is especially due to the inability of the approach to account for crack coalescence. As a result, more effort was required in the analysis of the results. More complicated 3D simulations to study deflection at cylindrical coated fibers are in progress and have been demonstrated,

but are quite challenging due to the previously cited limitations of the current implementation of XFEM.

In the presented study the parameter set was chosen to represent the melt-infiltrated SiC/SiC CMC HiPerComp®. Simulation results consistently predicted secondary crack initiation inside the interfacial coating at a significant distance in front of the primary crack. For the chosen set of parameters that were varied, the one that was predicted to have the greatest influence on the crack deflection mechanism was found to be the matrix strength, which was in all cases about an order of magnitude stronger than the fiber coating.

5. Acknowledgements

The authors would like to gratefully acknowledge discussions with Triplicane A. Parthasarathy and George J. Jefferson and thank them for helpful comments. The work was funded by the Air Force Research Laboratory under contracts FA8650-10-D-5226 and FA8650-10-D-5011.

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